

**THE INFLUENCE OF USING INSTAGRAM AS A PROMOTIONAL MEDIA FOR
BERDASI FISHERMEN'S VILLAGE BALIKPAPAN****I Wayan Sudarmayasa ¹****A Rinto Dwi Atmojo ²****Sabalius Uhai ³****Hanafi Husaini ⁴**^{*1,2,4} Diploma 3 Tourism Study Program, Samarinda State Polytechnic^{*3} Diploma 4 Travel business Study Program, Samarinda State Polytechnic**ABSTRACT**

The research entitled The Influence of Instagram Utilization as a Promotional Media for the Berdasi Fishermen's Village is expected to involve the community in the tourism area of the Berdasi Fishermen's Village Tourism Village, especially in terms of marketing their tourist village sustainably so that the current community and future generations can enjoy the results from generation to generation and maintain their regional traditions sustainably, especially in the field of culture, preserving the tradition of sustainable activities. One of the marketing strategies through social media is one of the bases for preparing a plan for developing the progress of a tourist village and making it a guideline for carrying out its activities in the tourist village, in addition to anticipating increasingly fierce competition in the future. The purpose of this study is to determine the concept of village management to increase competitiveness and good cooperation with local village managers. In this study, the author uses a research method with documentation, interviews and observations

Keywords:

Promotion, marketing strategy, handling work constraints

INTRODUCTION

With today's technological advances, people can use this digital era to do various activities, one of which is the use of social media as a means of marketing in the form of content and what is sold is not only that, with social media people can also be creative to sell products and services that they have, for example: food, drinks, clothing, and others. With the program that we run to provide education in general to make a product that will later be uploaded on social media look attractive and creative. Instagram is a photo sharing application that allows users to take photos and short videos, apply digital filters, then share them to various social media services including Instagram itself. Instagram features can be used on any iPhone, iPad or iPod Touch version with the iOS 3.1.2 operating system or later and any Android camera phone with the 2.2 (Froyo) operating system or later. This application is distributed through the Apple App Store and Google Play

Manap and Adzharudin (2013) are emphasizing the role of the Internet to develop tourist destinations, the same opinion is also expressed by Hanan and Putit (2014) where the contribution of social media as a driving factor to promote destinations. Both of their arguments show that the tourism industry and the Internet provide space to determine their decisions to make trips for tourists. Therefore, it is not surprising that the internet has basically changed the way travel information is searched for and the process of determining tourist destinations (Morosan & Jeong, 2008). The use of internet-based social media as a tourism communication medium is more flexible and profitable, because the use of media like this is considered easier, has a wide reach, and is cost-effective in communicating tourism, so this is what makes social media increasingly in demand for communication and promotion facilities. Social media is an internet-based media that makes it easy and even allows its users to easily participate, create and share their experiences and information. In addition to Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest, LinkedIn, and Path which are some of the favorite social media in Indonesian society, one of the fastest growing social media is Instagram. Based on the explanation above, the researcher chose the Instagram account @nelayanberdasi_id as the object of research. @nelayanberdasi_id is an Instagram account that specifically provides information and introduces tourist attractions in the coastal area of Karanganyar through photos and videos. The nature of Instagram social media which is real-time, emphasizes visuals, has various features, is easy to use and is efficient in introducing tourist attractions in Karanganyar Regency, making the Instagram account

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@nelayanberdasi_id have 1,563 active followers (taken on August 24, 2022). Interestingly, the Instagram account is managed personally by the child of the manager of the Berdasi fishing village and his colleague Rio voluntarily and not from the government or the Balikpapan city tourism office. Therefore, the researcher wants to know how Instagram is used as a promotional media in the Berdasi fishing village of Balikpapan city.

1.2. Research Objectives The purpose of this study is to determine how much social media is used, especially Instagram, in the development of Rural Tourism Villages and the position of social media promotion in supporting the promotion of increasingly advanced Tourism Villages in the future. The author feels that the problem in this study is very important to be implemented because a tourism village focuses on how much promotional media can be done by Rural Tourism Villages and its influence in supporting the management of Tourism Villages through available promotional media. With the problems above, the formulation of the problem is obtained, namely How to Utilize Instagram as a Promotional Media for Berdasi Fishermen's Village in supporting the management of Tourism Villages. The purpose of this study is to determine how much the marketing concept of Rural Tourism Villages and the position of social media promotion in supporting the promotion of increasingly advanced Tourism Villages in the future. Benefits of the study are For readers, this study is useful for understanding the concept of Rural Tourism Villages and the Utilization of Instagram as a Promotional Media for Berdasi Fishermen's Village. For the community, it can be useful as a reference for the need and importance of the role of the community involved in supporting the development of tourism in their area. Relevance of the Theme of this study entitled "The Influence of the Utilization of Instagram as a Promotional Media for Berdasi Fishermen's Village" is to determine the increasing role of social media in supporting activities in tourist villages and increasing

LITERATURE REVIEW

Promotion comes from the word "promote" in English which means development or improvement. Promotion is the art and technique of connecting with the public, introducing the products produced, services and facilities provided so that potential users know about them. According to Badollahi Mustafa, promotion is "a persuasive marketing communication mechanism by utilizing public relations techniques. Promotion is a forum for exchanging information between organizations and consumers with the main objective of providing information about products or services to those products or services. According to Rangkuti (2009:49) promotion is carried out by a company with the aim of informing the existence of the product and providing confidence in the benefits of the product to buyers. Promotion is one way used to increase sales volume. Consumer reactions to promotions can appear in various forms, from growing awareness of simply knowing the existence of the product to the act of buying or using it. Promotion is an important activity in a business organization. No matter how good the product or service produced, it is useless if it is not known and not determined by most consumers. Promotion Objectives According to Rangkuti (2009:51) in his book Creative Promotion Strategy and Integrated Case Analysis, companies carry out promotional activities with the main objective of seeking profit. Generally, promotions carried out by companies must be based on the following objectives: 1. Behavior modification. The market is a meeting place where people want to exchange activities, people consist of various kinds of behavior. Likewise, their opinions about a product or service, their interests, desires, drives, and loyalty to the goods and services are also different. Therefore, the purpose of promotion is to change the behavior and opinions of an individual, from those who initially did not accept a product, to being loyal to the product. 2. Providing Information. Promotional activities are intended to inform the target consumer about a product. This information is such as price, quality, buyer requirements, product uses, special features, and others. 3. Persuading. In general, this promotion is less popular with the public. However, in reality, this type of promotion is currently emerging. This promotion is carried out to encourage purchases. 4. Reminding. This reminding promotion is carried out to maintain the product brand in the hearts of the public. This promotion is carried out during the maturity stage in the product life cycle. Companies try to pay attention to and retain existing buyers, because buyers do not only make purchases once but must continue and continue. According to Rangkuti (2009:230) the indicators used in online promotion are: 1. Advertisements Indicators used in online IMC are links to other sites, as well as advertisements placed on the site in question. 2. Sales Promotion Indicators used are: (a) Offering something for free, (b) providing discount coupons or special offers, (c) providing programs related to loyalty programs, (d) holding programs related to lotteries and games (e) holding online games. 3. Public Relations Indicators used are: (a) a collection of questions frequently asked by consumers and answers or commonly called frequently asking questions, (b) press center, (c) press release, (d) photo gallery, (e) registration to receive e-newsletters, (f) testimonials or online guest books, (g) recommending the site to others, (h) free e-postcards or other forms of files that can be downloaded for free. 4. Direct Marketing The indicators used are: (a) telephone number, (b) fax

number, (c) address, (d) mailing address, (e) link to e-mail, (f) online response form, (g) sitemap, (h) search index, (i) virtual tour, (j) section explaining the latest things or what's new, (k) calendar of activities, (l) information about exchange rates, (m) jokes or cartoons, (n) location maps, (o) facilities for using other languages. 5. Personal Selling The indicators used are the availability of facilities that can make sales online, such as online booking facilities, making online reservations, making online sales, and various other online transaction facilities. Online payment methods should also be used, such as using credit cards and PayPal. It can be concluded that social media is a medium on the internet that allows its users to represent themselves and interact, collaborate, share, communicate with other users and form bonds

DISCUSSION

Balikpapan City is one of the regencies/cities in the province of East Kalimantan, Indonesia and one of the largest cities in Kalimantan besides Samarinda City, Balikpapan which is an industrial city certainly has great potential in all fields. Balikpapan City can be reached by various transportation routes and is visited by people outside Balikpapan, outside the province and even from abroad. Astronomically, Balikpapan City is located between 0 21'81 " - 01 09'16" South latitude and 116 15'16 " - 117 24'16" East longitude and is crossed by the equator or equator which is located at latitude 00. Meanwhile, the Kampong Berdasi area which is located within the Balikpapan City area is a cultural village located within the company area which is used as a superior program in supporting village areas around the area under the responsibility of the company concerned. The tourist attraction of Kampung Berdasi Not too far from the center of Balikpapan City and close to the access to SAMS (Sultan Aji Muhamad Sulaiman) airport in Balikpapan City makes Kampung Berdasi have a very strategic position to visit. The village area occupied by people who mostly work as fishermen is one of the villages that has very good potential in developing tourism Tourism Potential in East Kalimantan, especially Balikpapan City, is currently experiencing development. In addition to its potential as an industrial city as its attraction, Kampung Berdasi also preserves the culture of fishermen and historical relics that are worth knowing. The potential of the sea and some of its culinary tours are quite famous not only for local people but also for tourists from outside the area. The tourist village has very good potential as a destination that is quite worthy of being a tourist attraction. The infrastructure and facilities supported by the company are also adequate, starting from the parking location between small and large vehicle parking which is located separately. Guest facilities, public facilities such as toilets and other supporting facilities are quite comfortable. As support for the existence of a tourist village, there will also be a souvenir shop equipped with the needs of guest souvenirs.

From the aspect of attraction, there are several attractions that can be seen at this location, including Kampong fishermen berdasi is an area that is the Somber River area, precisely in Balikpapan City which has abundant fisheries potential in Indonesia as Geographically, this area is an estuary area that is directly connected to Balikpapan Bay. According to Balikpapan City Regulation No. 12 of 2012 [1], the Somber River Area is declared a fisheries designation area in Balikpapan City. Meanwhile, based on data from the Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries in 2020 [2], this area has an area of 227,456 hectares and has a fisheries potential of 808 tons/year and there are approximately 8 fishing groups with a total membership of more than 1000 people. Not only the sea products that make this area dominant by work as fishermen, there is also tourism potential that can be a job opportunity for the local community, the management of the tourist attraction of the tie-dasi fishing village is based on the inauguration of the formation of a fishing group consisting of 15 members. The problem is that the involvement of all registered members and also the surrounding community and the local government so that the development of the tie-dasi fishing village tourism potential is still minimal to be registered as one of the natural tourism destinations to the local Tourism Office, in this case the tie-dasi fishing village only carries out its duties as a fostered village of a company that distributes assistance in the form of funds every year. is that not all people are able to fully implement this pattern both in theory and in its application. With many who still do not understand and understand scientifically what tourism really is, the role of the village government in this case is very important and effective in supporting and pumping up the spirit of the community.

The second factor is the economic factor. People who are involved in tourism activities actually still have many jobs elsewhere. This is because their work and role so far in terms of economic income have not been economically reliable and have not been able to be used as a basis for their lives. So their role so far has been as a sideline in the world of tourism and the rest or it can be said that being involved in the world of tourism is only a reserve and not as a main job. Moreover, in this new life, it is required to provide equipment which of course requires costs. From this research, it is hoped that tourism industry entrepreneurs, policy makers and industry players to also pay attention to the role of society in the tourism world in empowering the potential that exists in a region. How

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tourism can act as an example and barometer for the opening of tourist attraction areas in promotional support not only from social media but also from other media that can be used in promoting, habits and living prosperously in maintaining the sustainability of destination development in their own regions. There are several forms of attention that village governments can provide to tourism actors, including from scientific factors, such as readiness of human resources, readiness of infrastructure and guaranteed economic income so that it can be relied on. The community can still make their destination one of the main sources of income that can be relied on. As for this output, it is hoped that a good pattern will be found for destination development. The hope is that it will also be published in writing that can be accessed by the community wherever they are so that it has a reference for all parties regarding the patterns and activities carried out at the destination

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is Promotional activities carried out on the Instagram account @nelayanberdasi_id are in the form of Instagram ads, giveaways, re-uploading consumer testimonials on instastory, photo collections on Instagram feeds, including telephone numbers, email addresses, directions and website addresses on Instagram profiles. In these promotional activities, Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi wants to be known as one of the tourist destinations with an educational character. This character is supported by content that always uses a photo background with a natural theme, interesting properties and also positive sentences that are always included in each upload. With this content, Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi hopes to spread joy and enthusiasm. The messages and information conveyed by @nelayanberdasi_id to consumers on its Instagram account contain informative elements. The hashtag created is #KampoengNelayanBerdasi which is included in every upload containing photos or videos about nature education. The purpose of promoting on the Instagram account @nelayanberdasi_id is to introduce Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi to more people and convey the values raised by Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi. The selection of Instagram as an active promotional media is based on the reason that Instagram has practicality and provides benefits for sales, namely by simply uploading photos or videos of products to an Instagram account, then the photos are seen by consumers and consumers are interested in buying. The advantages of Instagram are because the number of users is very large and continues to increase, making it easier to spread messages. The disadvantages of Instagram felt by Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi come from the assessment of people who think that good content is content with the most likes, while the number of likes obtained by photos or videos uploaded to @nelayanberdasi_id is not always large. Constraints in the use of Instagram social media in Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi before the author came to Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi from the posts we saw were untidy and tended to be messy, after that we conducted a joint evaluation to upgrade the Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi Instagram account. The impact of the use of Instagram in Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi after the author and fellow interns conducted an evaluation at Kampoeng Nelayan Berdasi we were able to provide a very influential impact because with the author and fellow interns, providing an explanation and training on how to promote using Instagram as a promotional tool, the results of the explanation and training we provided were used well and directed in terms of story posts, photos and videos.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the type of survey research used is a qualitative descriptive research method, where this study uses more qualitative data and also qualitative analysis, namely describing (describing) something specific from a particular situation (problem/subject) and assisted by related parties. The location of this research is located in the Kampung Nelayan Berdasi Tourism Village Area, Balikpapan City, East Kalimantan Province, which is a fostered village of PT Interport Mandiri Utama Balikpapan. Data and Data Sources Based on the source, the data in this study is grouped into 2, namely: Primary data sources, namely data obtained or collected from the first source or directly obtained at the research site in the Kampung Nelayan Berdasi Tourism Village Area, both verbally and in writing from respondents and informants. The data includes data from observations or observations, in-depth interviews with informants (community leaders, women leaders and also tourism business actors). And Secondary data sources are data obtained not from the first party but from certain parties related to this research, data sources in the form of related documentation, village profiles obtained from government institutions, previous research, literature studies or other references, places and events and related archives that exist. To collect data used in identifying problems, researchers use the following data collection methods Field Research (Observation, In-depth interviews, and Field Documentation) Documentation is used to facilitate observations in the field, facilitate further data studies and obtain a picture of the atmosphere in the field. To document conditions in the *berdasi* Area, as Literature Study, Documents and Library Study. Literature study is conducted to obtain relevant theories

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and literature to support research. The sampling technique used in this study is purposive sampling, namely the selection of a group of subjects based on previously known characteristics or properties of the population. For this reason, informants are selected who are considered to know and can be trusted as sources of relevant data and know the problems being studied in depth. Data Analysis Technique Data analysis is the process of simplifying data into a form that is easier to read and implement. Data analysis is carried out with the aim that the information collected will be clear and relevant. In accordance with the research objectives, the data analysis technique used to analyze the data in this study is qualitative descriptive analysis, with the research method used being the descriptive method, which is a data search technique used to obtain an overall picture of the object, which is studied through in-depth observation and interviews.

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